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Review Article

A REVIEW ON POLYHERBAL ANTI - LICE OIL**¹Ms. Priyanka R. Boratwar, ²Ms. Chitralkha G. Therkar, ³Ms. Jija K. Lode, ⁴Ms. Trupti R. Dumore, ⁵Ms. Esha R. Gurnule**Assistant Professor, Department of Quality Assurance,
Siddhivinayak College of Pharmacy, Warora, Dist. – Chandrapur, MH – India**Abstract:**

Head lice are insects parasitizing humans for many years. Natural products have been used in traditional medicine since long ago and have been an issue of interest since the costs are usually lower, and they are generally considered less toxic. Here we present an evidence-based review of plant compounds for treating head lice infestation. We conclude that many plant products, such as black pepper and hibiscus flower, promise new products to eliminate head lice infestation. Over-the-counter natural products should be supported by in vitro data and adequately designed controlled trials that evaluate cure rates and safety. Providing that a new family of synthetic insecticides is not discovered, plant products may replace chemical insecticides on the market in the future.

Keywords - Plant Compound, Plant Products, Less Toxic, Traditional Medicine

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INTRODUCTION:

Hair is one of the most characteristic features of mammals and has various useful objectives such as protection against external factors i.e. heat, cold, etc. Hair is one of the important parts of the body considered a protective appendage on the body and an accessory structure of the integument along with the sebaceous gland and sweat gland. The basic part of the hair is the roots, the bulb, and the shaft. Some common problems are related to hair, such as hair fall, dandruff, lice, split ends, and grey hair. A piece of hair looks simple but is one of the most complicated structures in the body.^[1]

Hair is made up of two structures,^[2]

1. Hair follicle—The hair follicle is where hair starts to grow and where it is held in place. It is a building-like structure that starts in the epidermis and extends to the dermis. The follicle is lined by an inner and outer sheath that protects and molds the growing hair and ends just before the opening of the sebaceous gland.

2. Hair shaft - The hair shaft is made up of keratin protein and it consists of three respective layers. Those layers are, The inner layer also called as medulla. Depending on the type of hair, the medulla is rarely present, and the middle layer, which is called the cortex makes up the majority of the hair shaft. The outer layer: is also called a cuticle, which is formed by tightly packed scales in an overlapping structure that resembles roof shingles.

3. Hair types - Hair type is primarily based on the type of curls of hair. The amount of twisting in the hair is objectified by the hair follicle. Hair type is decided by genetics.

Lice^[3]

Head lice are wingless insects that have been obligate parasites of humans for thousands of years. Before modern existence, humans shaved to remove head lice using various physical techniques or attempted to destroy them using various substances applied to the hair. Mutual grooming with the capture of lice by hand is a common practice still today in many areas. Archaeological discoveries of lice in coprolites show that captured lice were often eaten. Combs with teeth containing entrapped head lice have been seen commonly in the archaeological record.

Topical medicines applied to the hair using plant parts and plant derivatives, also known as 'natural products', would have been used in these times, but the record is inadequate. These botanicals likely contained phytochemicals, particularly secondary compounds, produced by plants. However, there is little other than anecdotal, traditional, or cultural proof on this topic.

Having head lice is called pediculosis and this is classified into two stages i.e. active pediculosis and inactive pediculosis. People with active pediculosis have live lice motile in the hair of the head or live embryos in viable eggs attached to hair shafts. Lice are tiny, wingless insects that infest the hairs, skin, and feathers of animals. Clinical signs include alopecia and occasionally anemia. Diagnosis is based on the inspection of injured sites and visualization of lice or nits. Many effective oral and topical treatments are available.

Head lice infection is linked with limited morbidity but causes a high level of anxiety among caregivers of school-aged children. Head lice have been companions of the human species since antiquity medical providers need to educate and reassure affected individuals and caregivers that head lice are neither a health hazard nor a symptoms of less hygiene and are not responsible for the spread of any disease. Despite this information, there is significant stigma resulting from head lice infestations in high-income countries or regions, resulting in children and adolescents being ostracized from their schools, friends, and other social events.

In the market, available of many synthetic chemical products are available for killing lice and their eggs but these chemical product causes some side effects such as itching, headache, hair fall, dizziness, and changing hair colors. So, we prepare and formulate natural and herbal Anti-lice oil for killing lice permanently by using natural products such as neem, amla, black pepper, clove, Brahmi, lemon, hibiscus flower, and leaves. These natural products can not cause any side effects.

Materials

Table 01 – List of Ingredients and Vendors

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Role of Ingredients	Vendors
01	Neem	Anti-Bacterial	Local Region
02	Brahmi	Smoothing Agent	A to Z medical stores
03	Amla	Anti-Oxidant	A to Z medical stores
04	Clove	Anti-Oxidant	A to Z medical stores
05	Black pepper	Anti-Parasitic	Local shop
06	Hibiscus flower	Hair growth stimulant	Garden
07	Lemon	Preservative	Garden
08	Liquid paraffin	Base	SVCOP Laboratory
09	Coconut oil	Base	Bharat Kirana store, Warora

Description -**1. Neem^[4]**

Synonyms - Neem tree, Margosa, Arishth

Biological source - It consists of the fresh or dried Leaves and seed oil of *Azadirachta indica* belonging to the family *Meliaceae*.

Chemical constituents – The most important active constituent is azadirachtin and the others are nimbolinin, nimbin, nimbidol, sodium nimbinat, guanine, salannin, and quercetin.

Uses – making softer your scalp, to promote hair growth, temporarily block hair follicles, soothe frizz, minimize greys, decrease dandruff, and treat head lice.

Habitat - India, Pakistan, Bangladesh
Description - Neem trees are found commonly in India, Africa, and America. due to having medicinal properties, it has been used in Ayurvedic medicine for many years. It is a fast-growing tree and can reach heights up to 15-20 meters. The Sanskrit name of neem is Arista. The US National Academy of Science recognized the importance of neem for solving global problems.

Roles -

1. Cure scalp problems and Prevent premature greying.
2. Makes lustrous and healthy hair.
3. Promote thicker, stronger hair growth.

2. Brahmi^[5]

Synonyms - Hydro cotyleasiatica

Biological source - It consists of leaves of *Centella Asiatic* belonging to the family *Apiaceae*

Chemical constitute - Triterpenoid, volatile and fatty acid, alkaloid, glycosides, flavonoids, other vitamins B, C, G, and some amino acid

Uses - This herb helps form a protective layer around the hair fibers.

Habit - India, China, Indonesia

Description - Centella Asiatica is known primarily as 'brain food' in India because it is one of the leading herbs used to treat hair loss, and skin problems, heal wounds, and activate nerve and brain cells. The leaves 1-3 from each node of the stem, have a long petiole, 2 to 6 cm long.

Role -

1. It may have an anti-inflammatory benefit
2. It enhances muscle coordination and it stimulates the hair growth.

3. Amla^[6]

Synonyms - Embilica, Indian gooseberry, Amla.

Biological source - It consists of the Dried fruit of *Embilica Officinalis* belonging to the family *Phyllanthaceae*.

Chemical constituent – Fruit consists of about 28% of the tannins in the whole plant. This tannin has two hydrolyzable forms. Embricanin A and Embricanin B are natural antioxidants. Embricanin A provides Ellagic acid, glucose, and Gallic acid when hydrolyzed, whereas Embricanin B is hydrolyzed to form Ellagic acid and glucose. Also present in vitamins, amino acids, fixed oils, and flavonoids like rutin and quercetin.

Uses - Promote healthy hair growth, boost volume, reduce dandruff, and treat head lice.

Habitat - Uttar Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Rajasthan, and Madhya Pradesh in India.

Description - Amla tree height grows up to 8 meters, Branchlets are 10 - 20 cm long. Amla leaves have a pinnate resemblance, very small, simple, and attached by the base to Branchlets. The colors of the flower are yellowish.

Role -

1. Reduce dandruff
2. Promote healthy hair growth and strengthen the hair root.

4. Clove ^[7]

Synonym - Clove flower, Clove buds, Lavang.

Biological name - It consists of dried flower buds of *Eugenia Caryophyllus* belonging to the family *Myrtaceae*.

Chemical constituents—Volatile oil; phenol chiefly eugenol, acetyl eugenol, Tannins.

Uses—stimulant, aromatic and internal preparation.

Habitat—India, Indonesia, Pakistan, Srilanka.

Description - Clove is mainly used in Ayurvedic. It is usually known as “lavang”. Clove is a precious spice, it is a member of Myrtaceae. Clove is mainly used in the preparation of various foods. Clove oil is used for antimicrobial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetes, and antioxidant properties. Eugenol, the most important composition of Clove oil, has been accepted as a food preservative by China, the US European Union, and other countries and regions.

Role –

1. Treating dandruff.
2. To fight hair loss.

5. Black Pepper ^[8]

Synonyms – Piper nigrum, pepper, Kali Mirch

Biological source – It consists of dried unripe fruits of *Piper nigrum Linn.* belonging to the family *Piperaceae*

Chemical constituent – Piperidine group of alkaloids, 1-2.5% volatile oil, Resin, starch, Arginine, Ascorbic acid, Carotene, Thiamine, and riboflavin.

Uses – Carminati, Antimalarial, Stimulant, stomachic, Flatulent, antiarthritis.

Habitat – Southeast Asian Asia

Description – Black pepper is one of the most widely used spices, valued for its characteristic sharp and stinging qualities. It is cultivated for its fruit that is usually dried and used as a spice seasoning and for other purposes. Black pepper is native to Southern India and is extensively cultivated in this tropical area. Black pepper is isolated from the green unripe fruits of the pepper plant by cooking in hot water. The heat breaks cell walls in the fruit, activating the browning enzymes during drying. Cooked fruits are dried in the sunlight for certain days, during which the fruit around the seed shrinks and darkens into a thin, wrinkled black layer.

Role –

1. Use as spices for making food.
2. Also, it is used in herbal hair oil.

6. Hibiscus flower ^[9]

Synonym - Rosids, Malvales

Biological Source – It consists of Dried flowers of *Hibiscus Rosa-Sinensis* belonging to the family *Malvaceae*

Chemical constituent – Alkaloids, L- ascorbic acid, Anthocyanin, Beta – carotene, Beta – sitosterol, citric acid, Polysaccharides etc.

Uses – Stop hair loss, prevent premature greying, and treat dandruff.

Habitat – U.S, Europe, India.

Description – The leaves are alternate, ovate to lanceolate, obtain with toothed or lobed margin. The flower is large conspicuous, trumpet shape, with five or more petals, color from white to pink, red, orange, peach, yellow, or purple, and 4-18 cm broad.

Role –

1. Stops hair loss and prevents premature greying.
2. Treat dandruff and thicken hair and add volume

7. Coconut Oil ^[10]

Synonym – Coconut oil, coconut butter.

Biological Source – It consists of the oil expressed from the dried solid part of the **endosperm of coconut, *Cocosnucifera L.*** belonging to the family *Palmae*

Chemical constituents – 90% saturated fatty acid and 10% unsaturated fatty acid.

Uses – Use in industrial applications for cosmetics and detergent production

Habitat – Kerala

Description – Coconut oil is an edible oil that has been consumed in tropical regions for thousands of years. Asithasa long shelf life and a melting point of 76 °F, it is used in baking industries. A negative campaign against saturated fats in general, and tropical oils, led to most food manufacturers abandoning coconut oil in recent years in favor of hydrogenated polyunsaturated oils, particularly soy, which consist of trans fatty acids. Studies done on populations consuming diets rich in coconut oil show no adverse effects on the health of the population.

Role –

1. Masks hair
2. Moisturizes hair
3. Seal hair
4. Mask hairs look shinier.

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